

Verifiable Contracting

A use case for onboarding and contract offering in financial services with eIDAS and Verifiable Credentials

Sérgio Manuel Nóbrega Gonçalves²[0000-0002-7818-4757], Alessandro Tomasi¹[0000-0002-3518-9400] Andrea Bisegna^{1,3}[0000-0002-8055-5262], Giulio Pellizzari²[0000-0001-6455-780X], and Silvio Ranise^{1,2}[0000-0001-7269-9285]

¹ Security & Trust, FBK, Trento (Italy) {a.bisegna,ranise,altomasi}@fbk.eu

² University of Trento, Trento (Italy)

{giulio.pellizzari,sm.nobregagoncalves}@studenti.unitn.it

³ DIBRIS, University of Genoa, Genoa (Italy)

Abstract. We investigate the combined use of eIDAS-based electronic identity and Verifiable Credentials for remote onboarding and contracting, and provide a proof-of-concept implementation based on SAML authentication. The main non-trivial value derived from this proposal is a higher degree of assurance in the contract offering phase for the Contracting Service Provider.

Keywords: Verifiable Credentials · Digital Identity Proofing · Digital Contracting

1 Introduction

From the point of view of a Service Provider (SP), offering a contract to a remote applicant can be a risky proposition. Reliably establishing firstly that someone not physically present really is who they claim to be, and secondly that the details they have provided to enter into a legally binding agreement with the SP are correct, is no trivial task. There are long established procedures to address these problems when the person is physically present, usually involving a form of photographic ID and any number of proofs of other details, such as utility bills to prove current address and/or bank statements to prove account numbers. In the case of remote applicants, however, digital solutions for identity proofing and remote contracting are still a work in progress. In this paper, our contribution is a proof-of-concept to test the combination of two recent and emerging technologies: electronic identity cards and verifiable credentials.

We consider a Contracting Service Provider (CSP) wishing to enter a legally binding contract with an applicant before providing their services. Important examples include utilities and telecoms. In establishing a legally binding contract, CSPs commonly incur costs due to fraud and erroneously entered information. Concretely, a utility billing the wrong bank account, or having to enter a legal dispute over information entered by an applicant during a past contracting

phase, will incur legal costs and delays. In this work we focus on the initial offering phase, in which a CSP wishes to have a high degree of assurance that the information being entered in the contract is correct before offering it to the applicant; our goal is to determine whether the combination of two innovative technologies can assist in this process.

As a concrete minimal example, we consider the case of a utility CSP requiring (a) an applicant’s personal information and (b) an applicant’s bank account number (IBAN). The eIDAS [10] framework is designed to enable a public service infrastructure for secure and remote identity proofing⁴, and the potential of eIDAS-based eID for strong customer authentication in the banking sector is well-known - see for instance [6]. The Verifiable Credentials W3C recommendation [26] is designed to enable the sharing of verifiable claims about subjects with cryptographic proofs of integrity and authenticity.

In this paper we examine how these two frameworks could be usefully combined in order to enable secure remote contracting. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first PoC combining the two technologies without recourse to Self-Sovereign Identity, e.g. as in the SSI eIDAS bridge [25]. The main non-trivial value derived from this proposal is a higher degree of assurance in the contract offering phase for the CSP. Considering the novelty particularly of the VC recommendation, our objective was first and foremost to test the practical feasibility of the idea; we leave a proper security assessment to future work.

In Section 2 we describe the use case and a scenario we propose to address it. In Section 3 we briefly summarize some of the relevant aspects of the technologies in our proposal. In Section 4 we describe our proof-of-concept implementation. Finally, in Section 6 we evaluate our findings.

2 Use case: contract offering

We consider the case of a utility CSP requiring (a) an applicant’s personal information and (b) an applicant’s International Bank Account Number (IBAN) in order to offer them a contract for services. In the case of an unknown applicant, this information will be considered Claims by the applicant and which the CSP will have to either verify or accept at their own risk. In order to mitigate against fraud, the CSP would prefer a high level of assurance in these claims, and a means of verifying that: the claims are correct and valid, the applicant at the time of offering is the same as the claim subject, and the issuer is a trusted party.

⁴ Identity proofing is the process of establishing that an unknown applicant really is who they claim to be, and is performed during customer onboarding (e.g. opening a new bank account); after onboarding, accounts are associated with an authenticator, and subsequently authentication is required for a remote claimant to access an enrolled identity’s resources (e.g. online banking). See [18].

2.1 Proposed use case scenario

Concretely, our proposal is to consider the IBAN to be an attribute of a Subject, and to have the Account Servicing Payment Service Provider (ASPSP) issue a Verifiable Credential to that effect. A rough component diagram of our proposal is shown in Figure 1.

Fig. 1: Entities involved in the proposal and their roles under the two main trust frameworks - eIDAS and VC.

From the perspective of identity management in the cybersecurity context of, e.g. SP 800-63B [18], the required information about the applicant can be considered as attributes of an identity, i.e. claims made about a Subject by an Issuer or Identity Provider (IDP) with some associated proofs of authenticity.

The Verifiable Credentials [26] W3C recommendation is designed specifically to enable the sharing of verifiable claims about subjects with cryptographic proofs of integrity and authenticity. In our use case, they can be viewed as a form of authorization certificates [19], for which it is critical for security purposes to map the authenticated identity to the certificate holder.

In order to accomplish this, Issuer (ASPSP) and Verifier (CSP) of the VC can identify the Subject by their eIDAS unique identifier (See Section eIDAS-based eID for identity proofing). The eIDAS framework is designed to enable a public service infrastructure for secure and remote identity proofing; the potential of eIDAS-based eID for strong customer authentication in the banking sector is well-known - see for instance [6]. For instance, one of the eIDAS-notified schemes is the Italian eID card, CIE 3.0, and its use as a means of identity proofing during remote onboarding is already explicitly permitted Italy Bankitalia AML

regulations, which state that authentication through an eIDAS-compliant scheme is sufficient to perform due diligence for the specific step of identity proofing, even without the physical presence of the applicant ([2] part 2 section III comma 2).

Using eIDAS, a citizen with an eID is the Subject of identity assertions by their national IDP. The Subject acting as a Subscriber first applies for an account at an Account Servicing Payment Service Provider (ASPSP, in the sense of PSD2), then receives a contracting offer from a Contracting Service Provider (e.g. utilities or telecoms).

Using Verifiable Credentials, the ASPSP issues a verifiable claim tying an account number to the Subject; the Subject holds the claim in their wallet, and presents the claim to the CSP in order to receive a contract offer.

At a high level, the proposed steps would be the following:

1. Requester, in possession of eID, requests a new account with Account Service Provider (ASP)
2. ASP performs automated remote identity proofing with eID through “login with eIDAS”
3. Bank issues a VC with the requester’s eID “PersonIdentifier” as subject and the new IBAN as attribute
4. Requester requests a contract offer from Service Provider (SP)
5. SP performs automated remote identity proofing with eID through “login with eIDAS”
6. SP verifies VC of type IBAN and matches VC subject attribute with eIDAS “PersonIdentifier”

3 Background: eIDAS and SAML SSO

3.1 eIDAS-based eID

eIDAS allows Relying Parties (RP) to receive assertions on a core attribute set [12] of eID bearers from the eIDAS attribute profile. Between member state eIDAS nodes, the protocol chosen for such assertions is SAML v2 [24]. For natural persons, the core attributes are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1: eIDAS attributes for natural persons ([12]).

Mandatory	Optional
Current Family Name	First Names at Birth
Current First Names	Family Name at Birth
Date of Birth	Place of Birth
Unique Identifier	Current Address
	Gender

The Unique Identifier field can be leveraged by VC issuers to identify claim subjects. The assertion by the member state IDP on mandatory attributes can be leveraged by the CSP in the contracting phase. A list of notified eIDAS schemes is informally maintained by the eID User Community [9]. The eIDAS interoperability framework [11] enables each member state to notify one or more eID schemes based on different technology and processes, from national identity cards to mobile-based solutions. The eIDAS regulation [10] establishes a Level of Assurance (LoA) for each scheme - low, substantial, or high. Minimum requirements for each LoA set out in [7], and guidelines on how each scheme may concretely attain an LoA are published by the Cooperation Network [8]. Security considerations on eIDAS compliant eID schemes have also been published by ENISA [14].

The security of eIDAS schemes has been the subject of scrutiny in [13]. The security properties of each scheme depend on its technology and processes. Cooperation Network guidelines offer some clues as to the properties that can be expected from each LoA; for instance, a substantial LoA requires the means of authentication to be based on at least two factors and be demonstrably under the control of the subject to whom it belongs (e.g. one biometric and/or knowledge factor), whereas the high LoA requires additional protection against duplication, tampering, and use by others. By way of example, CIE 3.0 has been accorded a high LoA; it contains a chip with Common Criteria certification against duplication and tampering, and the private key in the chip is unlocked by PIN number, thereby providing factors of possession and knowledge during authentication. CIE 3.0 chip specifications [23] have more detail on compliance with PACE and EAC mechanisms for authentication, confidentiality, and integrity.

3.2 SAML SSO

In this paper we consider the SAML 2.0 Web Browser SSO Profile [24] (SAML SSO) since the concrete eID scheme we have in mind is based on a SAML 2.0 IDP [20], and the web browser profile fits our use case (Section 2) and our implementation (Section 4). Fully mobile and hybrid scenarios are also considered in the documentation but beyond the scope of the present proof of concept.

Three entities are involved: a Client (C), an Identity Provider (IDP), and a Service Provider (SP). C is a web browser with which a user interacts; the user's goal is to have access to a service or a resource provided by the SP. IDP authenticates C and issues authentication assertions that are trusted by SP - the SSO trust relationship is depicted with a handshake icon in Figure 2. SP uses the assertions generated by the IDP to decide on C's entitlement to the requested service or resource.

Figure 2 shows a Message Sequence Chart (MSC)⁵ of the main steps of the SAML SSO protocol, which we can briefly describe as follows:

⁵ Each vertical line in an MSC represents an entity, and horizontal arrows represent messages from one component to another. Identity management protocols are often expressed as MSC to identify any flaws.

Fig. 2: Message Sequence Chart (MSC) of the SAML SSO protocol [1].

S1 C asks SP to provide the resource at URI.

A1-2 SP sends C an HTTP redirect response (status code 302) for IDP, containing an authentication request $\text{AuthReq}(\text{ID}, \text{SP})$, where ID is a randomly generated string uniquely identifying the request (steps A1 and A2). A frequent implementation choice is to use the `RelayState` field to carry the original URI that C has requested (see [24]).

↔ IDP challenges C to provide valid credentials (dotted double arrows in the figure): this is not specified in the standard of the SAML SSO in order to accommodate any authentication process offered by IDP.

A3-4 If the authentication succeeds, IDP builds an authentication assertion as the tuple $AA = \text{AuthAssert}(\text{ID}, \text{C}, \text{IDP}, \text{SP})$ and embeds it in a response message $\text{Resp} = \text{Response}(\text{ID}, \text{SP}, \text{IDP}, \{AA\}_{K_{\text{IDP}}^{-1}})$ where $\{AA\}_{K_{\text{IDP}}^{-1}}$ is the assertion signed with IDP's private key (the key icon in Figure 2). IDP places Resp and the value of `RelayState` received from SP into an HTML form and sends the result back to C in an HTTP response (step A3) together with some script that automatically posts the form to SP (step A4).

S2 Finally, the SP sends C an accepted HTTP response (status code 200) containing the requested resource.

3.3 eIDAS-compliant certificates and PSD2

eIDAS-compliant Qualified Certificates conforming to ETSI TS 119 495 [15] are the standard for PSD2 API for both authentication (Qualified Website Authentication Certificates - QWAC) and non-repudiation / content commitment (Qualified Electronic Seal Certificates - QSealC).

The Berlin group access-to-account implementation guidelines [4] require mutual authentication of TPP and ASPSP using eIDAS- and RTS-compliant

Qualified Certificates, which must include all the roles for which the TPP is authorized. Open Banking Europe⁶ maintains a list of Qualified Trust Service Providers issuing PSD2-compliant Qualified Certificates.

4 Scenario and implementation

The entities involved in the scenario and their roles are:

1. eID holder - Subject of an IDP-issued eIDAS-based eID document
2. eID IDP
3. eID OCSP responder
4. ASPSP - Relying Party to IDP under eIDAS, QWAC and QSealC Subject under eIDAS, Issuer of VC
5. CSP - Relying Party to IDP under eIDAS, Verifier of VC

Our eID subjects are authenticated to SPs through an X.509 certificate, designed to resemble the basic elements of the Italian eID certificate specifications [23]. In particular, the Subject commonName field contains an unique identifier of the person independent of the individual certificate or document, the only allowed key usage is authentication (digital signature), and extended key usage is client authentication.

All the servers (entities 2-5) are developed using NodeJS, and their services have been configured to work over a secure communication channel (HTTPS) to protect them from man-in-the-middle attacks, in the protocol for the CIE 3.0 eID scheme as described in the manual for SPs [20]. Servers have two separate certificates, one for server authentication and one for non-repudiation. In general, these could be issued by any authorized CA; in our specific use case, we think it plausible that these would be Qualified Website Authentication (QWAC) and Qualified Seal Certificates (QSealC), respectively.

Our sample implementation is concerned mainly with the Service Provider part of the architecture supporting authentication and verifiable credential issuing and verification to support the use case. Our proof-of-concept implementation is available on github⁷. We give a high-level description here and refer the interested reader to the repository for implementation details.

4.1 SAML

The two SPs (entities 4,5) implement SAML through the [passport-saml](#) module. The IDP uses the [saml-idp](#) module.

After receiving the SAMLRequest from the SP, the IDP verifies if together with the authentication request the client has also provided the certificate. If that is the case, a verification process starts. The IDP checks if the client certificate has been signed by the Certification Authority (CA) it expects, whether it has

⁶ <https://www.openbankingeuropa.eu/qtspas-and-eidas/>

⁷ <https://github.com/stfbk/vc-saml-node>.

expired, and finally whether it has been revoked. The latter operation is achieved by an API call to the OCSP service, which exposes an API that accepts as input a certificate, checks if its serial number belongs to the list of revoked ones and returns ‘good’, ‘revoked’, or ‘unknown’ accordingly.

If all these checks are successful and the user grants access to their data to the SP, the SAMLResponse is generated and sent back to the SP, which parses it and shows the contained attributes.

The SAML implementation has been designed with a view towards integration with our container-based identity management training environment, Micro-Id-Gym [5].

4.2 Verifiable Credentials

Verifiable Credentials (VC) allow Issuers to issue Claims - signed statements about Subjects. Issuers are identified by a URI, Subjects may be identified by a URI or a set of attributes.

We highlight the following steps taken to adapt the VC data model [26] to our use case, and we note that the issuer has to provide information about itself and the credentials it has issued via specific endpoints, in a manner not unlike an identity provider. The endpoints are to be taken as following the issuer’s domain, `https://<issuer_host>`⁸. An example of an issued VC is shown in Listing A (Section A).

verification The VC has an embedded proof property constructed as a digital signature with the issuer’s non-repudiation private key, corresponding to their trust provider-issued non-repudiation certificate. The public key can be obtained from the controller document at the `/issuer` endpoint.

credential type and context We needed to introduce the subject attributes of eIDAS unique identifier and IBAN in the VC issued by the ASPSP. This was done by defining a custom context, which the issuer makes available through an `/credential/iban` endpoint.

issuance, expiration, and status Issuance and expiration dates are added, and a `/credential/status` endpoint can be called to check whether the VC has been revoked.

5 Related work

An application of VCs to a financial use case (KYC) was shown in [21], based on the FIDO UAF protocol in an adaptation described by the same authors in [22]. The subject is assumed to have already been enrolled with attribute authorities, which issue VCs that can be used as part of the KYC process. Broadly speaking, this use of VCs is similar to the one here proposed. However, FIDO is strictly an authentication protocol, not covering identification. In [22], a new public-private

⁸ In our simple nodejs-based proof-of-concept implementation, this is `localhost` followed by a port identifying the service provider.

key pair is created for each authenticator-service provider pair, so there is no such notion as a unique identifier for the subject; this is by design, for privacy reasons. The exclusive use of FIDO in this manner thus requires issuing a separate VC to the same subject for every new service provider, with an exponential increase in VCs to be managed, and seems counter-intuitive to the use case of contract signing.

In our proposal, the use of a unique identifier for the subject is one of the key features leveraged from eIDAS. The use of FIDO2 authenticators may then play an important role as part of eID schemes, for instance as proposed in a FIDO alliance white paper on the use of FIDO2 for eIDAS [17], either using the authenticator in lieu of the eID card itself, or to authenticate the subject to a QTSP remotely storing their Qualified Certificate and private key.

6 Lessons learned and conclusion

Added value The main non-trivial value derived from this proposal is a higher degree of assurance in the contract offering phase for the Contracting Service Provider. While there are some costs and technical know-how required in becoming a Service Provider under eIDAS, these are predictable costs and expected to be quite small, as opposed to costs incurred as a consequence of fraud, litigation against repudiation, and plain errors due to manually entered data.

The ability to perform identity proofing remotely is of course highly valuable, but on its own it is enabled by eIDAS as an explicit design goal, and is not new or specific to this proposal. At the same time, for a financial use case it is extremely plausible to use an eIDAS login as a starting point since it strongly contributes to an ASPSP's AML compliance. The addition of Verifiable Credentials based on eIDAS is a synergy expected to enable an ecosystem of high-assurance contracting services.

ASPSP as VC Issuers The solutions adopted by financial services providers often form the gold standard for identity proofing and authentication, and in some cases banks act as identity providers themselves (e.g. BankID [3]). It is not unreasonable to assume that financial institutions would be willing to offer VC issuing services; the set-up involved is in some ways less onerous, in the sense that they do not require federation between Issuer and Verifier, and the Subject is responsible for their sharing.

With reference to the API commonly proposed to comply with PSD2, VCs also appear more adequate for sharing long-term information that may be considered an attribute of the subject, as opposed to live information about their ASPSP-managed account, such as availability of funds and initiation of payments etc. In our proposal, a contracting SP does not have to take the subject's identity attributes and request information about a related IBAN through a PISP; the SP can immediately match the subject's authentication to the subject of the VC and only has to verify the validity of the VC itself.

Contract signing We note that an important piece we have not covered in this proposal is how to close the contracting phase with an electronic signature carrying adequate legal weight (advanced or qualified) depending on CSP requirements. Just as legal persons can apply for a QSealC, natural persons can also be issued Qualified Certificates. eIDAS does allow remote electronic signatures, in which the qualified signature certificate is stored by the trust service provider, to which the subject authenticates. In any case, the signature process would require a careful study of client-side issues such as the informed consent by the signer, and their exclusive and secure control over the signing device and the keys within. Other factors such as cost and user experience would undoubtedly play a role. Since our focus here is the server-side logic and proof-of-concept for the back-end, we have not considered these issues for the moment.

Other remarks We have assumed that the Service Providers have a constant, resolvable online presence that adequately guarantees a resolvable address for all relevant endpoints, such as eSeal certificate, VC context, refresh, and revocation status endpoints. This seems to us a fair assumption where ASPSP are concerned.

We expect that for authentication purposes the overall scheme here described can inherit the security properties of the base eID scheme. Specific use case requirements may be met for instance by requiring a minimum eIDAS LoA, following e.g. Cooperation Network guidelines [8]. The VC data model does not specify strict validation procedures; while our proposal is closely modeled on PKI standard practices for issuance, verification, and revocation of claims, we have not performed a thorough security analysis at this stage.

Lastly, in the same way that Financial API are undergoing a standardization process, such as the one being carried out by the FAPI working group [16], VCs would benefit from a reference API without regard of the underlying service infrastructure.

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A Listings

Listing 1.1: Example of a Verifiable Credential for the use case described in Section 2.

```
1 {
2   "@context": [
3     "https://www.w3.org/2018/credentials/v1",
4     "https://<issuer_hostname>/credential/iban"
5   ],
6   "id": "https://<issuer_hostname>/credential/<
7     serialNumber>",
8   "type": ["VerifiableCredential", "ibanCredential"],
9   "issuer": "https://<issuer_hostname>/issuer",
10  "credentialSubject": {
11    "eIDASUniqueIdentifier": <eIDAS unique identifier>,
12    "iban": <iban>
13  },
14  "issuanceDate": <datetime>,
15  "expirationDate": <datetime>,
16  "credentialStatus": {
17    "id": "https://<issuer_hostname>/credential/status
18      /<credentialSerialNumber>",
19    "type": "OCSP-like"
20  },
21  "proof": {
22    "type": <signatureType>,
23    "created": <datetime>,
24    "jws": <jws>,
25    "proofPurpose": "assertionMethod",
26    "verificationMethod": "https://<issuer_hostname>/issuer#nonRepudiationKey"
27  }
28 }
```

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